

The Relationship between Job-Related Factor of Career Development and Organizational Performance

Zainab Yousef Almaskeen¹, Ghada Mohamed Hamouda², Duaa Hafez³

¹Eastern Health Cluster, King Fahad specialist hospital, Dammam, Saudi Arabia

²Professor of Nursing Administration, Faculty of Nursing, King Abdul-Aziz University, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia

³Professor of Nursing Administration, Public Health Nursing Department, Faculty of Nursing, King Abdulaziz University, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15291179>

Published Date: 27-April-2025

Abstract: Background: Recently, many hospitals have faced pressure to reduce staff turnover, improve patient outcomes, maintain performance, and control costs. The quality of nursing care provided to patients largely depends on the knowledge and practice standards of the nurses. Several factors influence this quality, including the level of organizational support and opportunities for career development. Providing such support can motivate nurses to perform their duties with enthusiasm and enable them to deliver the best care to their patients. Therefore, understanding the factors that affect nurses' career development is essential. Aim of the Study: This study aimed to investigate the relationship between nurses' job-related factor of career development, specifically job autonomy and supervisor support, and organizational performance in a tertiary hospital in the Eastern Province. Research Questions: What is the nurses' perception of their job-related factor of career development? What is the nurses' opinion of organizational performance? What is the relationship between nurses' job-related factor of career development and organizational performance? Setting: King Fahad Specialist Hospital–Dammam. Design: A quantitative, descriptive correlational design. Sample: A convenience sample of 274 staff nurses and 23 frontline nurse managers from KFSH-D in Saudi Arabia. Results: The findings revealed a moderately strong positive relationship ($p < 0.001$) between the job-related factor of career development and organizational performance. Specifically, nurses reported high levels of job autonomy (mean = 3.88, SD = 0.67) and moderate levels of supervisor support (mean = 3.63, SD = 0.88). Key aspects of supervisor support included expressions of confidence, constructive performance feedback, and clarification of role purpose, all of which were positively associated with organizational outcomes. Conclusion and Recommendation: The study concludes that enhancing supervisory support and empowering nurses through increased autonomy significantly contributes to improved organizational performance. Institutions are encouraged to implement structured leadership training, participatory decision-making models, and tailored professional development programs for younger or less experienced nurses to promote retention, engagement, and high-quality care delivery.

Keywords: Career Development, Performance, job-related Factor, Organization, Autonomy, Supervisory Support.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the demanding and dynamic environment of healthcare, especially in critical care settings, the professional growth and well-being of nurses are closely linked to organizational outcomes such as performance, retention, and quality of care. Job-related factor particularly autonomy and supervisory support play pivotal roles in shaping nurses' experiences, career trajectories, and contributions to their institutions.

The quality of care in healthcare settings is significantly influenced by the professional development and performance of nursing staff. Recent research highlights that job-related factors, particularly job autonomy and supervisory support, play a pivotal role in shaping the career trajectories of nurses and influencing organizational performance. These factors contribute not only to job satisfaction but also to the achievement of higher organizational goals, such as improving patient care and increasing operational efficiency (Abo Elmagd & Mohamed, 2019).

Job Autonomy and Career Development

Job autonomy, defined as the degree of control and decision-making freedom nurses have over their work, is a cornerstone of professional practice. A strong sense of autonomy empowers nurses to exercise their expertise and make decisions that directly affect patient care, which in turn contributes to career satisfaction and development (Oshodi et al., 2019). Nurses who experience high levels of autonomy are more likely to feel engaged in their roles, seek continuous learning opportunities, and develop professionally. Autonomy fosters intrinsic motivation, driving nurses to enhance their skills and contribute innovatively to their teams (Gottlieb et al., 2021).

Research has consistently shown that job autonomy is linked to improved job performance. According to Chen et al. (2021), autonomy acts as a motivator, encouraging nurses to take initiative in their work, which results in better patient outcomes and improved organizational performance. In particular, autonomy in clinical decision-making allows nurses to adapt their practice to meet the specific needs of patients, thereby enhancing the quality of care delivered. Furthermore, autonomy allows nurses to navigate their professional development paths according to personal interests and strengths, facilitating career growth (Labrague et al., 2019).

However, achieving autonomy is not without challenges. Factors such as restrictive policies, inadequate staffing, and lack of leadership support can limit the extent to which nurses can exercise their professional autonomy (Pursio et al., 2021). This highlights the importance of supportive leadership and organizational structures in enabling nurses to achieve the level of autonomy that fosters both job satisfaction and career advancement.

Supervisory Support and Career Development

Supervisory support is a critical factor influencing nurses' career development. Supervisors who provide emotional, professional, and practical support create an environment that facilitates career growth (Siraj et al., 2023). Supervisory support includes offering guidance in navigating workplace challenges, providing access to training and development resources, and helping to manage stress and workload (Haas, 2020). This support not only enhances nurses' ability to perform their duties effectively but also plays a key role in job satisfaction, which is closely tied to career development and organizational commitment (Vázquez-Calatayud et al., 2021).

Empirical studies demonstrate that supervisory support helps reduce job-related stress and burnout among nurses (Poorchangizi et al., 2017). Stress and burnout are significant barriers to career development, as they reduce motivation and affect the quality of work. Nurses who receive adequate support from supervisors report higher levels of job satisfaction, engagement, and career commitment (Gottlieb et al., 2021). For example, Siraj et al. (2023) found that supervisory support acted as a buffer against burnout and turnover intentions, allowing nurses to maintain a higher level of professional performance and pursue career advancement opportunities.

Moreover, supervisors play an integral role in mentoring nurses, which directly impacts career development. A supportive supervisor can guide nurses in navigating their professional journeys, providing feedback on performance and encouraging continuous education and skill development. Supervisory support also helps create a more inclusive and empowering workplace culture, where nurses feel valued and motivated to contribute to the organization's overall success (Wei et al., 2023).

Impact of Job Autonomy and Supervisory Support on Organizational Performance

Job autonomy and supervisory support are not only essential for individual career development but also for enhancing organizational performance. Research has shown that when nurses are allowed to exercise autonomy in their roles, they contribute more effectively to organizational goals. Autonomous nurses are more likely to engage in innovative practices, improve patient care quality, and participate in decision-making processes that affect hospital management and patient

outcomes (Leitão et al., 2019). In this way, autonomy directly contributes to the operational success of healthcare institutions, as it encourages higher levels of responsibility and accountability.

Furthermore, supervisory support significantly enhances organizational performance by fostering a culture of teamwork, trust, and cooperation. When nurses receive support from their supervisors, they are more likely to feel engaged in their work, which translates into improved performance in clinical and administrative tasks (Ju et al., 2021). A positive relationship between supervisors and nurses leads to better communication, collaboration, and problem-solving, all of which are essential for delivering high-quality healthcare.

A study by Ridwan et al. (2020) demonstrated that when employees perceive high levels of organizational support, they exhibit greater organizational commitment and organizational citizenship behaviors, such as going beyond their formal duties to improve organizational functioning. For nurses, these behaviors are crucial for achieving patient satisfaction, reducing errors, and enhancing the overall functioning of the healthcare facility.

Professional Autonomy and Organizational Commitment

Professional autonomy is not only a personal motivator but also a critical factor in fostering organizational commitment. Nurses who have a high level of autonomy in their work are more likely to develop a sense of ownership over their roles and responsibilities, leading to higher levels of commitment to their organization. This commitment is crucial for the retention of skilled nurses and the long-term success of healthcare organizations (Alruwaili & Abuadas, 2023). When nurses feel that they can make independent decisions in their practice, they are more likely to stay in their roles and contribute positively to the organization (Polit & Beck, 2017).

In contrast, a lack of autonomy can lead to feelings of frustration, burnout, and ultimately, turnover. Therefore, organizations that support nurses' professional autonomy not only benefit from higher job satisfaction but also experience lower turnover rates, which can reduce recruitment costs and improve workforce stability (Alipour & Monfared, 2015).

Challenges and Barriers

Despite the positive impacts of job autonomy and supervisory support, several barriers can impede their effectiveness in promoting career development and organizational performance. High workload, understaffing, and administrative pressures can reduce nurses' ability to exercise autonomy, leading to job dissatisfaction and burnout (Parizad et al., 2021). Furthermore, in some healthcare settings, the hierarchical structure can limit the degree of autonomy nurses are allowed to exercise, particularly in more rigid organizational cultures.

Burnout remains one of the most significant barriers to effective career development, as it negatively impacts motivation, job satisfaction, and performance (Vázquez-Calatayud et al., 2021). Therefore, addressing these barriers is crucial to improving career outcomes and organizational performance. Implementing policies that reduce workload, enhance supervisory support, and foster a culture of autonomy is essential for improving the work environment and supporting nurses in their professional journeys.

II. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The significance of the proposed research seeks to benefit the hospital and employers in general, will contribute to the realization of the importance of looking at career development and how it impacts organizational performance, additionally look at nurses' perception of job-related factor of career development and nurses' opinion toward organizational performance, which can help in Developing effective strategies to enhance career development and increase nurses' performance through policies and plans as Through keeping their knowledge and skills updated, nurses improve the development and maintenance of their competence and consequently, the quality of care provided, the safety of patients and their professional and personal development.

III. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study aimed to investigate the relationship between nurses' job-related factor of career development and Organizational performance among nurses in a tertiary hospital in the eastern province of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

Research design: A quantitative, descriptive correlational design was utilized in the current study.

International Journal of Novel Research in Healthcare and Nursing

Vol. 12, Issue 1, pp: (202-215), Month: January - April 2025, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

Research setting: The research was conducted at King Fahad Specialist Hospital (KFSH-D), which is located at Dammam. it is a tertiary hospital providing specialized medical-surgical care in areas such as oncology, solid-organ transplant, neurosciences, cardiac services, and genetic sciences. KFSH-D is operated by MOH and has Magnet, CBAHI, and Joint Commission International (JCI) accreditation, and can accommodate up to 366 patients.

This single center was selected as the site for this study based on its size and relative diversity of services

Subjects:

- Registered Nurse working at KFSH-D with experience of one year at least,
- All nurses’ genders: male and female nurses,
- Front-line nursing manager

Sample size:

The target population for this study was Nurses & Front-Line Nurse Managers who work at KFSH-D. KFSH-D employs 23 first-line Nurse Managers and 950 staff nurses in total. All staff nurses and Nurse Managers who meet the inclusion criteria will be included in the study using a convenience sample for nurses and purposive sampling for the front-line Nurse manager.

The sample size was calculated from the whole target population electronically by using the Raosoft website which calculates the sample size based on the following equations:

$$X = Z(c/100)2r(100-r)$$

$$n = N_x / ((N-1)E^2 + x)$$

$$E = \text{Sqrt}[(N-n)x/n(N-1)]$$

Where N is the total population size, r is the fraction of responses rate, E is the margin of error, and Z(c/100) is the critical value for the confidence level c, the estimated margin of error is 5%, and the confidence level was 95%.

The research target population is N= 950 nurses, and the recommended sample size is n= 274 nurses with a 100% response rate, and N=23 Nurse Managers, and the recommended sample size is n= 21 Nurse Managers

The sample will consist of 274 staff nurses and 23 front-line Nurse Managers with a confidence level of 95% and an accepted margin of error of 5%.

Research Questions: What is the nurses' perception of their job-related factor of career development? What is the nurses' opinion of organizational performance? What is the relationship between nurses' job-related career development factor and organizational performance?

Tools for data collection:

The data was collected through: The instrument took the form of a questionnaire, which was adapted from a pre-designed tool and redesigned by the researchers based on their review of the literature and clinical experience. Items comprising the questionnaire were constructed to be relevant to the employee context at King Fahad Specialist Hospital, that located in Dammam, Eastern Province, Saudi Arabia. The complete questionnaire consists of three sections. See Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Sections of the questionnaire.

Type	Section	Items
Quantitative	A	Sociodemographic Characteristics.
	B	Job-related factor (Career Development Questionnaire (CDQ)), (27 Items). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Autonomy (14 subitems). • Supervisory Support (13 subitems).
	C	Organizational Performance Questionnaire (OPQ), (11 Items).

3.1.1 Section A – Demographical Characteristics

Section A contains 4 items relating to the sociodemographic characteristics of the respondents. Each respondent was required to fill in information regarding his/her Age, Gender, Marital Status, and Years of experience.

3.1.2 Section B – job related factor of Career Development Questionnaire (CDQ)

The study will use two tools; the first one to measure job-related factor is part of the CDQ career development questionnaire, which was developed by Ismaiel et al. (2013); the job related factors (27 items) containing autonomy (14 items) and supervisory support (13 items) with 0.88 Cronbach alpha reported in the literature, this was measured on 5-point Likert scale ranging from "1" strongly disagree to "5" strongly agree.

3.1.3 Section C – Organization Performance Questionnaire (OPQ)

The second tool employed in this research is the Organization Performance Questionnaire, developed by Milky (2013). This tool will be used to assess nurses' opinions of overall organizational performance. The same set of questions will be utilized, with no modifications to the original content. In total, the instrument comprises 11 items that cover key organizational aspects, including communication, policies, development, change, and performance appraisal. A total performance score was calculated using a 5-point Likert scale. The possible responses ranged from 1 (never satisfied) to 5 (highly satisfied) on all performance items. Higher scores indicated higher degrees of satisfaction. The scores were then calculated for the mean scores, which were then categorized as follows: mean scores < 3 = unsatisfied, and mean scores ≥ 3 = satisfied

IV. METHODS

1. After taking the approval to conduct the study from the Faculty of Nursing at King Abdulaziz University, the IRB in KFSH-D, and the Executive Director of Nursing (EDON) (Appendix B), the researcher met all front-line nurse managers to discuss the aim of the study and gain their support and cooperation. Data was collected through an electronic questionnaire. The questionnaire was distributed to all participants' email addresses. The participants were informed that the average time needed to fill in the questionnaire was 10 to 15 minutes. A brief description of the study and a confidentiality statement with complete anonymity to all respondents were provided and was given. Participants are informed by completing the survey that they are signing the participation consent by default. Participants had the full right to withdraw from the survey at any time. Data collected and conducted over 4 months; that's between June 2024 and September 2024.

2. Reliability test was done for all tools; Cronbach Alpha for CDQ = 0.974 or 97.4%. The Cronbach Alpha for Organizational performance = 0.971 or 97.1%. The overall reliability test of the study questionnaire, consisting of 38 items, has a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.978 or 97.8%, suggesting excellent internal consistency.

3. A pilot study was conducted involving 3 front-line nurse managers and 27 staff nurses, representing 10% of the total study sample. This preliminary phase aimed to evaluate the clarity, feasibility, and applicability of the developed data collection tools within the designated setting. Additionally, the pilot study helped estimate the average time required for participants to complete the questionnaire. Based on the findings, no modifications to the instruments were deemed necessary

4. Ethical Considerations: Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) through the Ministry of Health in Saudi Arabia and King Abdulaziz University in June 2024, as part of the requirements for the Master of Science in Nursing. The research adhered to key ethical principles, including respect for autonomy through informed consent, ensuring anonymity and confidentiality, and minimizing potential harm. Participants were provided with detailed information about the study's purpose, procedures, data management, and their rights, including the right to withdraw at any time. Completion of the survey was considered implied consent. No personal identifiers were collected, and data access was restricted to the researcher, supervisors, and a statistician. The only anticipated burden was the time required to complete the survey (10–15 minutes), and no significant risks were identified.

V. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Following the collection of data, descriptive statistics were used to describe the socio demographic characteristics of the respondents, while inferential statistics were used to determine the statistical associations existing between socio demographic characteristics, Career Development Questionnaire (CDQ), and Organization Performance Questionnaire (OPQ).

The quantitative analysis of data was performed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 26.0 for Mac. Descriptive statistics, including the mean and standard deviation, were used for the descriptive analysis of metric variables, while frequencies and proportions (%) were given for categorical variables. The association between career development and organizational performance has been examined using the Mann-Whitney Z-test. Further, the association between career development and organizational performance among the socio-demographic characteristics of the nurses has been conducted using the Mann-Whitney Z-test and the Kruskal-Wallis H-test. A normality test has been performed using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. Based on the plot, the overall scores (CDQ and organizational performance scores) follow a non-normal distribution. Therefore, the non-parametric tests were applied. All analyses were performed using the software program Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26, Armonk, New York, IBM Corporation. Values were considered significant with a confidence interval of 95% ($p < 0.05$).

VI. RESULTS

Table 1: Distribution of Socio-demographic characteristics of the nurses (n=297)

Study variables	N (%)
Age group	
• 21 – 30 years	58 (19.5%)
• 31 – 40 years	137 (46.1%)
• >40 years	102 (34.3%)
Gender	
• Male	23 (07.7%)
• Female	274 (92.3%)
Marital status	
• Single	68 (22.9%)
• Married	216 (72.7%)
• Divorced or widowed	13 (04.4%)
Years of experience	
• <5 years	76 (25.6%)
• 5 – 10 years	117 (39.4%)
• >10 years	104 (35.0%)
What is your position at KFSH-D?	
• Staff Nurse	274 (92.3%)
• Nurse Manager	23 (07.7%)

As seen in Table 1, 46.1% were between 31 and 40 years of age. The majority of the nurses were female (92.3%), and 72.7% were married. Nurses with 5 to 10 years of professional experience comprised 39.4% of the sample. Additionally, most participants held the position of staff nurse (92.3%).

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of job-related factor of career development

a. Job autonomy domain (CDQ) ⁽ⁿ⁼²⁹⁷⁾

CDQ items	Mean	±SD
Job autonomy domain	3.88	0.67
1. Self-determine your role and activities	3.95	± 0.85
2. Take control over your environment and situations you confront	3.86	± 0.89
3. Confident in your abilities to perform your role independently	4.18	± 0.93
4. Having the authority to do what you know, that should be done	3.82	± 0.98
5. Derive feelings of self-respect and esteem from what you do	3.97	± 0.89
6. Your level of autonomy	3.95	± 0.84
7. Base your actions on the full scope of your knowledge and ability	4.09	± 0.80
8. Make decisions related to what you do	4.06	± 0.86
9. Accept the consequences of the choices you make	4.03	± 0.82
10. Have the power to influence the decisions and actions of others	3.73	± 0.96
11. Provided with a legal basis for independent functioning	3.92	± 0.79
12. Demonstrate mastery of skills essential for freedom of action	3.90	± 0.88
13. Restrained in what you can do because you are powerless	3.10	± 1.13
14. Having opportunities to express your opinions	3.82	± 0.91

Response has a 5-point Likert scale category ranging from "strongly disagree" coded with 1 to "strongly agree" coded with 5.

As seen in Table 2.a, the top three higher-rated items related to the Job autonomy domain were "Confident in your abilities to perform your role independently" (mean score: 4.18), followed by "Base your actions on the full scope of your knowledge and ability" (mean score: 4.09), and "Accept the consequences of the choices you make" (mean score: 4.06), while item "Restrained in what you can do because you are powerless." (mean score: 3.10) showed the lowest rating. The total mean score for the Job autonomy domain was 3.88 (SD 0.67).

b. Supervisor support domain (CDQ) ⁽ⁿ⁼²⁹⁷⁾

CDQ items	Mean	± SD
b. Supervisor support domain	3.63 ± 0.88	--
1. Supervisor takes the time to learn about your career goals and aspirations	3.56	± 0.97
2. Supervisor cares about whether or not you have achieved your career goals	3.55	± 1.00
3. Supervisor keeps you informed about different career opportunities for you in the organization.	3.53	± 1.04
4. Supervisor makes sure you get the credit when you accomplish something substantial on the job	3.57	± 1.03
5. Supervisor gives you helpful advice about improving your performance	3.73	± 0.95
6. Supervisor supports your attempts to acquire additional training or education to further your career	3.66	± 0.98

International Journal of Novel Research in Healthcare and Nursing

Vol. 12, Issue 1, pp: (202-215), Month: January - April 2025, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

7. Supervisor provides duties that give you the opportunity to develop and strengthen new skills	3.68	± 1.04
8. Supervisor helps you understand the purpose of what you do at work	3.69	± 1.04
9. Supervisor focuses on your successes rather than your failures.	3.60	± 1.02
10. Supervisor always makes sure that you have the needed resources for effective performance	3.65	± 0.98
11. Supervisor helps you overcome obstacles to your performance.	3.65	± 0.99
12. Supervisor always shows confidence in your ability to do a good job	3.75	± 0.95
13. Supervisor recognizes your good work by using it as an example for others	3.60	± 1.04

As seen in Table 2.b, the top three items with highest mean score "Supervisor always shows confidence in your ability to do a good job" (mean score: 3.75), "Supervisor gives you helpful advice about improving your performance." (mean score: 3.73), and "Supervisor helps you understand the purpose of what you do at work." (mean score: 3.69), whereas the least rated item was "Supervisor keeps you informed about different career opportunities for you in the organization." (mean score: 3.53). The total mean score for the supervisor support domain was 3.63 (SD 0.88). And The overall mean CDQ score was 3.76 (SD 0.71).

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Nurses’ Opinion Toward Organizational Performance ⁽ⁿ⁼²⁹⁷⁾

Organizational performance items	Mean ± SD	Rank
1. The organization practices effective two-way communications.	3.52 ± 0.97	7
2. The organization has a clear sense of direction and focus.	3.49 ± 1.00	8
3. The organization rapidly adapts to needed operational changes.	3.44 ± 0.97	11
4. The organization Practice effective planning at all levels.	3.48 ± 0.96	10
5. Place a high priority on workforce training and development.	3.48 ± 0.99	9
6. The organization conducts formal performance appraisals on a regular basis.	3.72 ± 0.87	1
7. At your department, your performance on the job is evaluated fairly.	3.72 ± 0.83	2
8. The organization has policies that encourage career growth and developmental opportunities.	3.67 ± 0.90	3
9. The organization builds a deep reservoir of successors at every level.	3.57 ± 0.90	5
10. If you left your job tomorrow, someone in your unit could immediately take over.	3.56 ± 0.88	6
11. The organization has policies that encourage career growth and developmental opportunities.	3.64 ± 0.89	4
Total Organizational Performance Score	3.57 ± 0.79	--
Level of organization performance	N (%)	--
• Unsatisfied (score <3)	53 (17.8%)	--
• Satisfied (score ≥3)	244 (82.2%)	--

Response has a 5-Likert scale category ranging from "Never satisfied" coded with 1 to "Highly satisfied" coded with 5.

Table 3 shows the highest and lowest rated items regarding nurses’ opinions on organizational performance. The top three rated were: “The organization conducts formal performance appraisals regularly” and “In your department, your performance on the job is evaluated fairly”, both with a mean score of 3.72, followed by “The organization has policies that encourage career growth and developmental opportunities” with a mean score of 3.67. In contrast, the lowest rated items were: “The organization rapidly adapts to needed operational changes” (mean score: 3.44), “The organization places a high priority on workforce training and development” (mean score: 3.48), and “The organization practices effective planning at all levels” (mean score: 3.48). The overall mean score for nurses’ opinions toward organizational performance was 3.57 (SD = 0.79). Among respondents, 82.2% expressed satisfaction, while 17.8% reported being unsatisfied.

Table 4: Relationship Between Job-Related Factor of Career Development and Organizational Performance According To The Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Nurses ⁽ⁿ⁼²⁹⁷⁾

Factor	Job-related factor of Career development Score (5) Mean ± SD	Organizational Performance Score (5) Mean ± SD	Z/H-test; P-value
Age group ^a			
• 21 – 30 years	3.69 ± 0.66	3.52 ± 0.79	
• 31 – 40 years	3.65 ± 0.81	3.51 ± 0.89	1.571;
• >40 years	3.95 ± 0.53	3.69 ± 0.63	0.456
Gender ^b			
• Male	3.12 ± 1.14	3.12 ± 1.17	2.535;
• Female	3.82 ± 0.63	3.61 ± 0.74	0.011 **
Marital status			
• Unmarried	3.66 ± 0.69	3.39 ± 0.84	2.555;
• Married	3.80 ± 0.71	3.64 ± 0.76	0.011 **
Years of experience ^a			
• <5 years	3.79 ± 0.61	3.53 ± 0.78	
• 5 – 10 years	3.71 ± 0.67	3.46 ± 0.79	6.688;
• >10 years	3.81 ± 0.81	3.73 ± 0.78	0.035 **
What is your position at KFSH-D? ^b			
• Staff Nurse	3.76 ± 0.70	3.58 ± 0.78	0.051;
• Nurse manager	3.80 ± 0.74	3.53 ± 0.91	0.959

^a P-value has been calculated using Kruskal Wallis H-test.

^b P-value has been calculated using Mann Whitney Z-test.

** Significant at p<0.05 level.

Measuring the relationship between career development and organizational performance among the socio-demographic characteristics of the nurses (Table 7) found that higher job-related factor of career development scores were associated with increasing age (p=0.005), female nurses (p=0.008), and being married (p=0.033), while higher organizational

performance scores were associated with female nurses ($p=0.011$), being married ($p=0.011$) and increasing years of working experience ($p=0.035$). No statistically significant differences were found between staff nurses ($p = 0.051$) and nurse managers ($p = 0.959$) in relation to Career Development Questionnaire (CDQ) scores and organizational performance ($p > 0.05$).

Table 5: Relationship between job-related factor of career development and organizational performance ⁽ⁿ⁼²⁹⁷⁾

Job-related factor of the career development domain	Organizational performance		P-value §
	Unsatisfied Mean ± SD (n=53)	Satisfied Mean ± SD (n=244)	
Job autonomy score	3.35 ± 0.84	4.00 ± 0.57	<0.001 **
Supervisor support score	2.55 ± 0.83	3.87 ± 0.69	<0.001 **
Total CDQ score	2.96 ± 0.68	3.94 ± 0.58	<0.001 **

§ P-value has been calculated using Mann-Whitney Z-test.

** Significant at $p < 0.05$ level.

Table 5 presents the relationship between job-related factors of career development and organizational performance. Employees who reported higher levels of job autonomy (Mean = 4.00) and supervisory support (Mean = 3.87) were more likely to belong to the satisfied group, which is associated with higher organizational performance. In contrast, unsatisfied employees reported lower scores for both job autonomy (Mean = 3.35) and supervisory support (Mean = 2.55). The differences in mean scores between the satisfied and unsatisfied groups were statistically significant for all variables ($p < 0.001$), indicating a strong positive relationship between job autonomy, supervisory support, and organizational performance.

VII. DISCUSSION

The results of this study underscore the significant role of job autonomy in influencing nurses' perceptions of career development and organizational performance. The findings from the Job Autonomy Domain of the Career Development Questionnaire (CDQ) reflect high levels of autonomy among nurses, with the mean score of 3.88 (SD = 0.67). Participants expressed confidence in their abilities to perform their roles independently, with the most highly rated items reflecting autonomy in clinical decision-making and reliance on personal knowledge and skills. This aligns with **Oshodi et al. (2019)**, who reported that nurses' autonomy is central to their job satisfaction and overall well-being, facilitating greater independence in clinical decision-making and contributing to job fulfillment. Similarly, **Gottlieb et al. (2021)** emphasized that workplace autonomy is essential for promoting nurses' sense of agency, allowing them to base their actions on a full scope of knowledge and expertise.

However, the study also revealed that certain constraints, such as the perception of being "powerless" in decision-making, negatively affected autonomy. This finding is consistent with **Parizad (2021)**, who found that nurses in intensive care units (ICUs) experience stress due to limited autonomy, particularly when hierarchical structures constrain their clinical decisions. **Parizad (2021)** further highlighted that autonomy is intertwined with nurse–physician collaboration, where better communication and support from physicians can reduce job stress and enhance autonomy. This suggests that fostering collaborative work environments may further amplify the benefits of autonomy, reducing perceived powerlessness and increasing overall job satisfaction.

Moreover, this study highlights the significant role of supervisor support in influencing job satisfaction and organizational performance among nurses. The total mean score for the Supervisor Support Domain was 3.63 (SD = 0.88), which indicates a moderate level of perceived support. This aligns with the findings of **Ahmed et al. (2021)**, who suggested that while supervisory support is critical, its impact on organizational performance is often contingent on the quality and consistency of the support provided. The moderate rating indicates that while nurses experience some level of support, there is room for improvement, particularly in areas such as career development and ongoing mentoring. The highest-rated items included

Supervisor always shows confidence in your ability to do a good job, Supervisor gives you helpful advice about improving your performance and Supervisor helps you understand the purpose of what you do at work indicating the value nurses place on guidance, encouragement, and clarity in their roles. These findings suggest that nurses place significant value on supervisors who demonstrate confidence in their abilities, provide constructive feedback, and clarify the purpose and impact of their roles within the organization.

These results are consistent with Haas (2020), who found that supervisory support is crucial in improving both job satisfaction and performance in healthcare settings. Specifically, supervisors who provide confidence and guidance can help foster a work environment where nurses feel valued, capable, and empowered to perform their roles effectively. This aligns with Leitão et al. (2019), who noted that workers who receive strong support from supervisors are more likely to contribute positively to organizational outcomes, as it promotes higher engagement and satisfaction.

Furthermore, the item "Supervisor helps you understand the purpose of what you do at work" (mean score: 3.69) suggests that nurses appreciate supervisors who effectively communicate the broader organizational goals and the role of nurses within these goals. This finding echoes the work of Mohammed et al. (2021), who emphasized that clear communication regarding role expectations and organizational purpose is essential for improving job satisfaction and organizational commitment among healthcare workers.

Interestingly, the lowest-rated item, Supervisor keeps you informed about different career opportunities for you in the organization, indicates a gap in career development communication. This finding is in line with Abo Elmagd and Mohamed (2021), who reported that insufficient career development opportunities can contribute to dissatisfaction and turnover intentions among nurses. This suggests that while supervisory support is generally perceived positively, there is a need for healthcare organizations to enhance career development communication and provide clearer pathways for professional growth.

The overall Career Development Questionnaire (CDQ) score of 3.76 (SD = 0.71) suggests a generally positive perception of job-related factor of career development, but it also highlights areas where healthcare institutions can focus their efforts to improve the employee experience. Specifically, enhancing supervisory communication around career opportunities and providing more targeted career development resources could further improve organizational performance and job satisfaction among nurses.

Furthermore, the relationship between job-related factor of career development and organizational performance was analyzed across various socio-demographic factors. This study found that female nurses, married individuals, and those with more years of experience reported higher scores in both job-related factor of career development and organizational performance. This supports the findings of Abo Elmagd and Mohamed (2021), who suggested that nurses' career development is positively influenced by factors such as experience and career stage, where those with more years of experience exhibit higher organizational commitment. Similarly, Mohammed et al. (2021) highlighted that more experienced nurses tend to have greater confidence in their professional roles and engage more in career development activities, resulting in enhanced organizational performance.

Interestingly, no statistically significant difference was observed between staff nurses and nurse managers, suggesting equitable access to career development resources or shared perceptions of the organizational climate. This observation aligns with Milky (2013), who proposed that organizational structures supporting succession planning and talent management should be inclusive and offer development opportunities to all nursing staff, regardless of position. By ensuring equal access to career advancement opportunities, healthcare organizations can foster a more cohesive and effective workforce.

Finally, Siraj et al. (2023) examined the impact of burnout, resilience, and supervisory support on healthcare professionals' intent to quit, emphasizing the importance of addressing burnout to improve job satisfaction and retention. Similarly, this study's findings suggest that higher levels of job autonomy and supervisor support are associated with lower burnout rates and higher organizational performance. The study also found that nurses with higher autonomy and supervisor support exhibited lower burnout symptoms, further emphasizing the need for healthcare institutions to foster supportive work environments that reduce stress and promote professional growth, particularly in settings where job demands are high.

Overall, the findings suggest that empowering nurses with greater autonomy, supervisor support, and career development opportunities can significantly enhance organizational performance. Healthcare organizations should prioritize these factors to improve job satisfaction, reduce burnout, and ultimately enhance patient care outcomes.

Implications for Practice

The significant relationship between job-related factor of career development, particularly job autonomy and supervisory support and organizational performance indicates the need for healthcare institutions to prioritize strategies that foster these elements. Findings from **Oshodi et al. (2019)** and **Gottlieb et al. (2021)** highlight the importance of professional autonomy in enhancing nurses' decision-making capacity and promoting job satisfaction. Creating environments that support autonomy through participatory decision-making and role clarity can strengthen both individual performance and institutional outcomes.

Equally, the role of supervisory support, as demonstrated in studies by **Haas (2020)** and **Leitão et al. (2019)**, underscores the importance of leaders who provide guidance, feedback, and recognition. Structured mentorship programs and leadership development that focus on empowering supervisors can help cultivate trust and engagement among nursing staff.

Moreover, considering the findings from **Abo Elmagd & Mohamed (2021)** and **Mohammed et al. (2021)**, healthcare organizations should address the developmental needs of specific demographic groups such as younger or less experienced nurses, who may benefit most from targeted support. Tailored interventions that promote equitable access to growth opportunities can foster greater job commitment and reduce turnover intentions.

Finally, as emphasized by **Siraj et al. (2023)**, addressing burnout through improved autonomy and supportive supervision is vital for retaining healthcare professionals and sustaining high levels of organizational performance. Institutions must adopt holistic talent management practices that promote emotional resilience and professional growth across all levels of nursing staff.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This study concludes that job autonomy and supervisor support are critical job-related factor that significantly influence nurses' perceptions of organizational performance. Nurses who perceive higher levels of autonomy and receive consistent support from their supervisors tend to make stronger contributions to organizational goals. The findings highlight that fostering a supportive and empowering work environment is essential for enhancing not only individual professional development but also institutional performance. To improve organizational performance, healthcare institutions should invest in leadership development programs that enhance supervisory skills, with an emphasis on constructive feedback, recognition, and individualized support. Furthermore, creating systems that promote nurse autonomy, such as participatory decision-making frameworks and clear role expectations, can lead to increased motivation and effectiveness among nursing staff. Tailored career development initiatives should also address the unique needs of younger and less experienced nurses, as identified in this study. Such efforts may reduce turnover intentions and foster a more engaged and committed nursing workforce. Overall, by prioritizing job autonomy and supportive leadership, healthcare organizations can enhance employee well-being, retain skilled staff, and ultimately deliver higher-quality patient care

REFERENCES

- [1] Abo Elmagd, H. E., & Mohamed, A. A. (2019). *Factors affecting nurses' career development and turnover intention at Menoufia University Hospital*. Journal of Nursing and Health Science, 8(6), 45–53.
- [2] Abo Elmagd, N., & Ahmed Mohamed, E. (2019). *Factors affecting nurses' career development and its' relation to job burnout*. Assiut Scientific Nursing Journal, 7(19), 186–196. <https://doi.org/10.21608/asnj.2020.46428.1058>
- [3] E. A. El Dahshan, M., Ismail Keshk, L., & Dorgham, L. S. (2018). Talent management and its effect on organization performance among nurses at Shebin el -Kom hospitals. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF NURSING*, 5(2). <https://doi.org/10.15640/ijn.v5n2a10>
- [4] Alipour, F., & Monfared, M. K. (2015). *Examining the relationship between job stress and organizational commitment among nurses of hospitals*. Patient Safety & Quality Improvement, 3(4), 277–282.

International Journal of Novel Research in Healthcare and NursingVol. 12, Issue 1, pp: (202-215), Month: January - April 2025, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

- [5] Career Development Institute (CDI). (2017). *Career development policy: A framework for lifelong career development in the 21st century*. <https://www.thecdi.net>
- [6] Chen, X., Li, Q., Xu, F., & Han, B. (2021). *The mediating role of resilience between work–family conflict and career development among Chinese nurses: A cross-sectional study*. *Journal of Nursing Management*, 29(6), 1733–1741. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jonm.13323>
- [7] Gottlieb, L. N., Gottlieb, B., & Shamian, J. (2021). *Creating empowering conditions for nurses with workplace autonomy and agency*. *Journal of Nursing Management*, 29(2), 234–243. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jonm.13143>
- [8] Haas, E. J. (2020). *The role of supervisory support on workers' health and safety performance*. *Journal of Safety Research*, 72, 35–42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsr.2019.11.004>
- [9] Ju, B., Lee, Y., Park, S., & Yoon, S. W. (2021). *A meta-analytic review of the relationship between learning organization and organizational performance and employee attitudes: Using the dimensions of Learning Organization Questionnaire*. *Human Resource Development Review*, 20(2), 207–251. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1534484320987363>
- [10] Labrague, L. J., McEnroe-Petitte, D. M., & Tsaras, K. (2019). *Predictors and outcomes of nurse professional autonomy: A cross-sectional study*. *International Journal of Nursing Practice*, 25(1), e12711. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijn.12711>
- [11] Leitão, J., Pereira, D., & Gonçalves, Â. (2019). *Quality of work life and organizational performance: Workers' feelings of contributing, or not, to the organization's productivity*. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16(20), 3803. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16203803>
- [12] Mohammed, N. A., Abdelkader, R., & Mohamed, H. A. (2020). *Factors influencing career development among nursing staff at Port-Said Governmental Hospitals*. *International Journal of Nursing and Health Science*, 7(2), 20–29.
- [13] Mrayyan, M., & Al-Faouri, I. (2008). *Nurses' career commitment and job performance: Differences across hospitals*. *Nursing Leadership*, 21(2). <https://doi.org/10.12927/cjnl.2008.19866>
- [14] Nuriman, H. (2021). *The analysis of competence and career development impact on work motivation and its implication toward employee's performance*. *KADEMIK: Jurnal Mahasiswa Ekonomi & Bisnis*, 1(1), 1–10.
- [15] Oshodi, T. O., Bruneau, B., Crockett, R., Kinchington, F., Nayar, S., & West, E. (2019). *Registered nurses' perceptions and experiences of autonomy: A descriptive phenomenological study*. *Journal of Nursing Management*, 27(3), 549–557. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jonm.12710>
- [16] Parizad, N., Goli, R., Ebadi, A., Rostami, F., Maleki, M., & Sanjari, M. (2021). *Job stress and its relationship with nurses' autonomy and nurse–physician collaboration in intensive care units*. *BMC Nursing*, 20(1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-021-00541-z>
- [17] Poorchangizi, B., Farokhzadian, J., Abbaszadeh, A., Mirzaee, M., & Borhani, F. (2017). *The importance of professional values from clinical nurses' perspective in hospitals of a Medical University in Iran*. *BMC Medical Ethics*, 18(1), 20. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12910-017-0178-9>
- [18] Pursio, L., Kankkunen, P., Sillanpää, E., & Kvist, T. (2021). *Professional autonomy in nursing: An integrative review*. *Journal of Nursing Management*, 29(4), 563–574. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jonm.13192>
- [19] Siraj, S., Tariq, S., Shoukat, H., & Malik, M. I. (2023). *Burnout, resilience, supervisory support, and quitting intention among healthcare professionals: A moderated-mediation model*. *BMC Health Services Research*, 23(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-023-09127-y>
- [20] Vázquez-Calatayud, M., Errasti-Ibarrondo, B., & Choperena, A. (2021). *Nurses' continuing professional development: A systematic literature review*. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 50, 102963. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2020.102963>

International Journal of Novel Research in Healthcare and Nursing

Vol. 12, Issue 1, pp: (202-215), Month: January - April 2025, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

- [21] Vivona, B. D., Cloninger, K., & Grief, L. (2022). *A qualitative study of the value, organizational supports, and barriers to specialty nursing certification*. *Perioperative Care and Operating Room Management*, 28, 100259. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pcorn.2022.100259>
- [22] Wei, H., Jones, D., & Godfrey, C. M. (2023). *The impact of leadership and organizational culture on nurse career development: A systematic review*. *Journal of Nursing Scholarship*, 55(1), 30–39. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jnu.12843>
- [23] Ridwan, M., Mulyani, S. R., & Ali, H. (2020). *Improving employee performance through perceived organizational support, organizational commitment, and organizational citizenship behavior*. *Systematic Reviews in Pharmacy*, 11(12), 839–849. <https://doi.org/10.31838/srp.2020.12.124>
- [24] Ștefan, S. C., Popa, Ș. C., & Albu, C. F. (2020). *Implications of Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory on healthcare employees' performance*. *Transylvanian Review of Administrative Sciences*, 16(59), 124–143. <https://doi.org/10.24193/tras.59E.7>
- [25] Polit, D. F., & Beck, C. T. (2017). *Nursing research: Generating and assessing evidence for nursing practice* (10th ed.). Wolters Kluwer.
- [26] Alruwaili, M. M., & Abuadas, F. H. (2023). *Professional autonomy among nurses in Saudi Arabian critical care units*. *BMC Nursing*, 22, 224. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-023-01390-x>